

Modern Methods of Teaching Monologue and Dialogue Speech in Foreign Language

Buranova Lola Uktamovna

Senior teacher of the Department “English language and Literature”, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: The article analyzes the specifics of monologue and dialogue speech and considers the problem of teaching this type of speech activity of students in foreign language classes. Particular attention is paid to the levels and parameters.

Keywords: monologue speech, dialogue speech, pedagogical activity, problem, research.

Appeal to the development of such an important methodological problem as teaching monologue and dialogue speech of philology students is due to its relevance for their future profession. The professional development of a future English teacher is a complex and multifaceted process, the most important aspect is the formation of both the general and professional culture of the teacher.

The high culture of an English teacher assumes as close as possible to the level of an educated native speaker the possession of all types of speech activity, including oral monologue speech in all its manifestations, in particular, a public lecture that focuses many problems (the creative nature of oral speech, speech activity and linguistic personality).

The need to equip students with such a means of influence (training, development and education) as oral monologue speech is dictated by the fact that pedagogical activity is associated not only with the possession of all types of speech activity, various genres of oral speech, but also with the solution of creative problems in a certain worldview, spiritual and moral context. Graduates of Uzbekistan, having come to work in schools and other educational institutions in their homeland, should, with the help of various forms of work and teaching aids, including lexical and phraseological, textual material, educate their students in the spirit of kindness, love, tolerance and peacefulness.

A modern graduate of a language university should have developed skills of foreign language communication in the conditions of professional activity, during which there is a need to express their point of view on issues of interest, justify it, comment on information on read foreign-language sources. Thus, the issues of developing effective methods for teaching students of language universities oral monologue and dialogue speech based on an authentic written text are attracting more and more attention. At the same time, the problem of teaching oral speech is of particular importance, not only in senior, but also in junior courses, since the foundations of foreign language proficiency are laid here.

The development of dialogue speech in a foreign language being studied is one of the most acute problems of modern pedagogical science. This is confirmed by a number of studies, articles, manuals that have appeared recently. And, nevertheless, this problem requires further methodological resolution, since the modern requirements for dialogue speech - to teach students to talk in the foreign language being studied - are not always and fully met.

The current situation requires a new search for a more rational methodology for teaching dialogue speech, in which the desired practical results would be achieved in the shortest possible

way, with a minimum expenditure of time and effort, and the learning process itself would become feasible, interesting and exciting for students. Despite the fact that dialogue speech is more complicated than monologue, both from the point of view of tension of attention, and from the point of view of the variety and quality of speech samples used, and for a number of other reasons, nevertheless, from the point of view of consistency in teaching oral speech, preference should still be given dialogue speech. After all, it is through dialogue that individual speech patterns, entire structures are worked out and remembered, which are then used in monologue speech.

Speaking about the tasks of teaching dialogue, it should be noted that the method of teaching dialogue speech has recently emerged as an independent aspect of teaching oral speech. There are still many questions in this area that require theoretical and experimental research. These include: the ratio of dialogue and monologue speech, principles and techniques for creating a communicative environment in the classroom, features of speech perception in the process of dialogue, selection of situations that underlie teaching dialogue at different stages of learning, ways to create a dialogue speech situation in the classroom, selection dialogue teaching material.

Dialogue is a form of speech in which there is a direct exchange of statements between two or more persons. Any dialogue is based on various statements, the combination of which makes up its essence. By purpose, it is generally accepted to distinguish declarative, interrogative and incentive statements, each of them can be affirmative and negative. Narration consists in a message (positive or negative) about some fact of reality, phenomenon, event. Questions are intended to encourage the interlocutor to express an idea that interests the speaker. Motivating statements express the will of the speaker: order, request, prayer, threat, advice, offer, warning, consent, permission, refusal, call, invitation to joint action, desire. Dialogue speech has its own characteristics in relation to the selection, design and functional orientation of the use of language material. So, for her, the use of introductory words, interjections, cliches, expressions of an evaluative nature, reflecting the reaction of the speaker to the information received, denying or confirming the expressed thought, expressing doubt, surprise and wish.

The dialogue is characterized by the widespread use of extralinguistic means of expressing thoughts: gestures, facial expressions, indications of surrounding objects. Correlation in speech of linguistic and non-linguistic signs is defined as situationality. Situation - a set of circumstances, conditions that create certain relationships, environment or situation - facilitates communication, helps to save language resources.

When teaching dialogue speech, the following main tasks are solved:

First, to give the concept of dialogue in all its diversity, in its natural form, so that students are convinced that the question-answer form is only a particular, albeit the most common, case of dialogic communication. Using various examples, it should be shown that speech will only then be lively, natural and truly dialogic if the content of the remarks includes greetings, messages, invitations, expressions of various kinds of feelings (surprise, gratitude, confidence, doubt), assessment of facts, etc. Secondly, to teach students the necessary replicas, to train them to the level of automatism when used in a particular situation. Thirdly, to teach them to exchange these remarks in appropriate situations, that is, to teach them to conduct the actual dialogue. The implementation of these tasks, in addition to purely methodological techniques, is directly assisted by the language material of textbooks with a system of lexical selections, special exercises and texts. As work experience has shown, one /of the effective means of creating a motive for foreign language communication of students is non-traditional teaching methods. A role-playing game is a kind of learning technique in which a student must speak freely under given circumstances, acting as one of the participants in foreign language communication. An obligatory element of games is the resolution of a problem situation. A role-playing game based on solving a particular problem. These include role-playing and dramatization. In methodological literature, role play is defined as spontaneous behavior, their reaction to the behavior of other people involved in a hypothetical situation. provides maximum activation of

the communicative activity of students. The search for a solution to the task at hand determines the naturalness of communication. The statement of the problem and the need to solve it also serve to develop students' critical thinking. And, finally, the need for careful thinking through the situation, finding the right solution develops logical thinking, the ability to argue and counter-argument, to convince the interlocutor.

The more often the teacher turns to theatrical performances in the classroom, the less time and effort is spent on getting to know the situation and setting tasks, and the more often students can change roles. This is very important for the development of speech behavior skills in different situations.

The use of theater in the classroom shows the high effectiveness of this technique, primarily for the development of skills and abilities of unprepared oral speech based on the motivation of speech actions. Few of the students remain indifferent to the opportunity to try their hand at acting, all become active participants or witnesses of the use of a foreign language; first, consciously, and then subconsciously, "tie" various speech turns to certain situations of communication; more confidently operate with them when performing communicative-oriented exercises; quickly master new vocabulary determined by the plot; subsequently, they easily cope with program tasks.

Thus, non-traditional methods of teaching dialogic speech give a strong motive for learning the language, they help to create a language environment that is close to natural. It becomes possible to activate on this basis almost the entire program lexical and grammatical material of the initial and subsequent stages of training. Students quickly master speech constructions and formulas (within certain situations), then automatically operate with them when performing communicative tasks of a different kind. Students will acquire a sense of language much faster. Such classes provide an additional opportunity for the development of listening skills: students perceive the speech of others by ear, allow them to get acquainted with the literature of the country of the language being studied; contribute to aesthetic education, familiarizing them with the culture of the country of the language being studied.

List of used literature:

1. Aryan M. A. «Using the educational potential of speech etiquette in a foreign language».
2. Borzova E. V. «Dialogical speech as a goal and means of teaching English»
3. Budnichenko E. P. «Teaching Dialogue Speech in English Lessons»
4. Bukicheva O. A. «Communication-oriented approach in teaching dialogic speech at the initial stage»
5. Буранова М.У « Использование нетрадиционных методов для чтения текстов различных жанров»
6. Gez N. I., Lyakhovitsky M. V., Mirolyubov A. A., Folomkina S. K., Shatilov S. F. «Methods of teaching foreign languages»
7. Gorskaya L. N. «The initial stage of teaching dialogic speech»